

K –factor Emulation in Different OTA Chambers

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Abstract—This paper discusses over-the-air testing chambers and the principles behind emulating Rician-distributed channel fading envelopes of the propagation channel. The discussed chambers are the classical reverberation chamber, the vibrating intrinsic reverberation chamber, the multi-probe anechoic chamber, the resonating cavity hybrid anechoic-reverberation chamber, and the aveguide hybrid anechoic-reverberation chamber.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multiple-antenna systems play a key role in 5G and beyond wireless systems, effectively transmitting, receiving, and manipulating electromagnetic radiation within specific frequency bands and spatial directions to improve overall system efficiency. Over-the-air (OTA) testing of antenna systems is essential at all stages, from design to certification [1]. Examples of devices are smartphones, tablets, access points, radio base stations, satellite stations, and radar systems. As the number of antenna elements and other components grows, individual measurements of all components at all stages become impractical, emphasizing the importance of system performance characterization. Devices shall function in diverse physical environments, each with specific performance requirements depending on the wireless system. A distinctive characteristic of many 5G and beyond devices is their spatial selectivity, reflected by the antennas’ directive radiation pattern, especially for beamforming antennas. Spatial selectivity results in time and spatial variation of the channel, which can be modeled by a deterministic and a stochastic component. The Rician probability distribution commonly describes the envelope statistics of these radio propagation channels. Therefore, OTA chambers shall be able to emulate prescribed Rician statistics. This paper discusses a few methods to achieve this goal in various measurement chambers shown in Fig. 1.

II. RICIAN STATISTICS AND OTA CHAMBERS

The literature on emulating Rician fading channels for OTA measurements is extensive. We will focus on our findings and suggest further reading, such as [1]. As well known, the Rician distribution depends on two parameters. The first is the average link power $\Omega = \nu^2 + 2\sigma^2$, where ν^2 and σ^2 are the

powers of the deterministic and the stochastic components of the propagating wave field, respectively. The second parameter is the K -factor, the ratio $K = \nu^2/2\sigma^2$ such as $0 \leq K < \infty$. The K -factor evaluates the severity of the fading. If there is no deterministic component, then $K = 0$, while in the other limiting case, if there is no stochastic component, then $K \rightarrow \infty$ [2]. The physical interpretation of these two channels is as follows. $K = 0$ models a fully scattered field known as the rich isotropic multipath (RIMP) channel, while $K \rightarrow \infty$ models a single plane wave, i.e., the free space channel. In [3], we proposed a classification of OTA testing environments enabling spatial-directional selectivity. Fig. 1 shows examples of the classical reverberation chamber (CRC), the vibrating intrinsic reverberation chamber (VIRC), a multi-probe anechoic chamber (MPAC), a resonating cavity hybrid anechoic-reverberation chamber (RC-HARC), and a waveguide hybrid anechoic-reverberation chamber (WG-HARC).

A well-designed CRC produces an isotropic field distribution on average, and the goal is to generate a field distribution with $K \rightarrow 0$, i.e., as low as possible. However, the first massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) channel emulation setup producing various K -factors at 1 GHz was experimentally investigated to reproduce diverse channels in [4]. Here, the idea is to realize narrowband propagation channels with different K -factors along a massive linear MIMO array. It was shown that this could be achieved by simple means, e.g., by combining different loadings and orientations of the chamber antenna. Different K -factors can be achieved at different chamber space points. The study presented here gave rise to the idea of generating different channels within a chamber using a phased array.

A similar, still more advantageous approach compared to the CRC to generate independent samples in an on-average isotropic propagation environment is the VIRC [5]. In [6], [7], a methodology is presented to generate narrowband single-input single-output (SISO) channels for both electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) and OTA test and characterization. The focus is on low K -factors, i.e., $K < 0.1$. The methodology investigates various factors, such as loading, chamber fluctuations, and frequency dependence. The considered bands in [6], [7] are between 670 and 2740 MHz.

While the CRC and the VIRC provide 3D field distributions in reverberation chambers, the MPAC technique is deployed in anechoic chambers. Instead of reflecting surfaces, circular or spherical array antennas are often used to generate multipath channels with various K -factors. In [8], a uniform circular array antenna of dual-polarized ultra-wideband dipoles generates

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Fig. 1. (a) A classical reverberation chamber (CRC) [4], (b) a vibrating intrinsic reverberation chamber (VIRC) [6], (c) a multi-probe anechoic chamber (MPAC) [8], (d) a resonating cavity hybrid anechoic-reverberation chamber (RC-HARC) [9], and (e) a waveguide hybrid anechoic-reverberation chamber (WG-HARC) [11].

various K -factors for a wave field distribution on the horizontal plane. The considered system produces an omnidirectional wave field distribution plus a deterministic component at the narrowband 2600 MHz band. In the considered study [8], the impact of the scattered field by the MPAC antennas was studied numerically and analytically for a wide range of K -factors, i.e., $0 < K < 100$ and also experimentally for nominal values $K = 0, 5, 33$ with good agreement.

To further take advantage of the inherent 3D field distributions inside CRCs, a compact antenna test range (CATR) is added to the setup in [9], [10], resulting in the RC-HARC technique. The idea is to capitalize on combining the RIMP and free space channels to emulate fading channels with various K -factors. The approach is practical because combining absorbers, attenuators, and splitters can produce a continuum of K -factors from the channel calibration inside the chamber. The papers [9], [10] focus on generating Rician channels for the OTA characterization of the beamforming performance of phased array antennas or MIMO antennas in general at the lower 5G FR2 bands (24.25-29.5 GHz). The generated channels covered a wide range of values with good granularity $0.12 < K < 12000$.

A chamber borrowing some ideas developed in [4] has been conceptualized in [12], resulting in the WG-HARC technique. A multipath environment can be realized by recruiting waveguide modes through the excitation of the chamber [12]. Numerical simulations have demonstrated that a wide range of Rician channels can be generated. In theory, all possible K -factors can be emulated, i.e., $0 \leq K < \infty$ [13]–[15].

III. CONCLUSION

Several OTA chambers and techniques for generating Rician distributions with diverse K -factors have been presented. Each has its capabilities and areas of improvement. Nevertheless, they offer a fascinating and relevant research area in the era of directional communications.

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